

TOPIC: THE IMPORTANCE OF ATTRACTING FOREIGN INVESTMENTS TO THE TOURISM SECTOR IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article comprehensively covers the current state of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan, its development trends, and the attraction of foreign investments to this industry. It discusses the main reasons and economic benefits of attracting foreign investments in the tourism sector. The article also covers the importance of foreign investments for developing tourism infrastructure, improving the quality of hotel services, expanding the transport and road network, and improving the personnel training system in the country. It provides information on the legal, institutional, and financial mechanisms for attracting foreign investments to the tourism sector, as well as ways to increase the competitiveness of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan and strengthen its position in the international tourism market through the attraction of foreign investments.

Keywords: Tourism sector, foreign investments, tourism infrastructure, hotel services, transport and road network, personnel training, competitiveness, international tourism market, tourism potential.

INTRODUCTION

The tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan has been rapidly developing in recent years and occupies an important place in the economic and social life of the country. In this regard, the importance of attracting foreign investments is growing. In particular, measures are being taken to develop territories with historical, cultural, ecological, and other tourist resources, improve infrastructure, and expand the scope of foreign investments to improve service quality.

At the same time, issues such as the modernization of the tourism sector, the attraction of foreign investments to the industry, the improvement of the personnel training system, and the strengthening of marketing activities are also of paramount importance. The attraction of foreign investments is an important factor for the development of tourism infrastructure, the construction of new hotel complexes and recreation facilities, as well as for increasing the competitiveness of the industry.

In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, emphasized that "our only correct path is the active attraction of foreign investments and the increase of exports," which is certainly not in vain. In general, the correct direction of investment activity and the active attraction of foreign investments ensure the clear manifestation of the development opportunities in all sectors and spheres of the economy.

Indeed, the priority tasks of the state policy in the tourism sector today are the creation of conditions for the development of domestic and inbound tourism, the formation of constant tourist flows, the creation of tourism infrastructure, the formation of highly profitable investment projects, and the improvement of investment activity mechanisms.

It is also necessary to emphasize the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev No. PP-20 dated January 12, 2024, "On measures to develop and promote barrier-free tourism infrastructure in the Republic of Uzbekistan." The resolution provides for the gradual implementation of large-scale reforms to address the existing problems in the tourism infrastructure, improve the quality of services provided in the industry, and actively promote national tourism products in world markets, as well as ensure the necessary conditions for the free movement of people with disabilities in tourism infrastructure and cultural heritage sites, and create equal opportunities for all citizens in tourism.

MAIN PART

Nowadays, the volume of investments in the tourism sector in Uzbekistan and the attention to domestic tourism are increasing. Since 2017, the tourism sector of Uzbekistan has been rapidly developing along with other sectors and has become one of the main directions of the state policy.

In a short period of time, an unprecedented set of regulatory legal documents, including the adoption of the Law on Tourism, has laid a solid legal foundation for the gradual reform of this sector.

One of the main instruments for the development of the tourism sector in our country is the investments made in this sector.

In particular, in 2021, within the framework of investment projects in the tourism sector, funds totaling 11.4 trillion soums were mastered, and 495 projects were implemented. Within the framework of the State Investment Program, in cooperation with local hokimiyats, investments of \$562.7 million were mastered, and 31 projects were launched in 62 projects worth a total of \$1.2 billion.

In 2022, a total of 735 projects worth 22.1 trillion soums were launched in the tourism sector, creating about 23,000 new jobs in the industry. As a result of attention paid to the development of entrepreneurship, investment attraction, and the establishment of competitive services, leading hotel brands such as Radisson, Wyndham, Hilton, Hyatt Regency, Ramada, Mövenpick, Mercure, Courtyard by Marriott, Minyoun, InterContinental Hotels Group, and Accor are entering our tourism market. They are organizing their activities not only in Tashkent, but also in Jizzakh, Bukhara, Samarkand, and Khiva based on market demand.

For the first time, the Global Investment Forum is being organized in Uzbekistan within the framework of the 25th Session of the UNWTO General Assembly. The forum is attended by over 634 representatives from more than 100 foreign countries, including more than 120 major foreign investors and 600 large

local companies. Within the framework of the forum, promising projects worth a total of \$3 billion are presented to investors.

Within the framework of the Summit of the Heads of State of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, a new tourist center with an area of 260 hectares has been created in the city of Samarkand, and 8 hotels (4 and 5 stars) of world standards have been launched. \$516.0 million was invested in this project.

In general, all this is aimed at improving the efficiency of reforms in the tourism sector in Uzbekistan, improving the tourism infrastructure, creating favorable economic conditions and factors, expanding the place and share of the sector in the economy, improving the quality of services, and increasing the attractiveness of tourism in our country.

During the first 10 months of 2023, the number of foreign tourists visiting Uzbekistan reached 4.9 million. It should be noted that in the last three years, the flow of tourists has increased by almost 3 times, and in 2021 the number of foreign tourists was 1.8 million.

For reference: In 2023, Uzbekistan was included in the list of the 50 best tourist destinations in the world in the Travel Lemming online travel guide and took the 9th place. This guide provides information about new destinations and unique destinations around the world every year and is read by more than 6 million travelers.

During the first 10 months of 2023, the export of tourism services amounted to \$1.83 billion. This figure was \$1,041.1 million in 2018. In 2023, tourism services exports are expected to reach \$2 billion due to a significant increase in the number of tourists.

For reference: Citizens of 91 countries in the world can use the visa-free regime to visit Uzbekistan. In comparison, 26 countries can visit Kazakhstan without a visa, 41 countries can visit Turkey, and 56 countries can visit Georgia without a visa.

The noted results indicate the great potential of the industry. Therefore,

attention is paid to further increasing the number of infrastructure facilities and effectively utilizing the potential of domestic tourism.

In order to assess the development of domestic tourism in Uzbekistan, a survey was conducted by TUIT specialists, in which 1,282 respondents from all regions of the country participated. The results of the survey showed that almost 50% of the trips carried out throughout the country fall on 4 regions - Samarkand (15.8%), Bukhara (9.4%), Tashkent region (10.6%) and Tashkent city (11.4%).

Also, to the question "in what form do you carry out the trip?", 81.2% of the respondents answered "independently", 15.5% "organized by the workplace", 2.4% "with the help of tour operators". The survey showed that our compatriots mainly travel by personal car (56.8%) and train (17.3%).

Based on the results of the survey conducted by TUIT specialists, the following proposals can be made to further develop domestic tourism:

Formation of a register of settlements with the status of "tourist neighborhood", "tourist region" and development of an electronic platform;

Formation of its own brand for each region, based on the main tourist potential.

For reference: In order to promote the tourist potential of the Republic and further increase the flow of tourists, funds have been allocated to 28 diplomatic missions of Uzbekistan in foreign countries, and the participation of national tourism stands and business entities was ensured in 16 international tourism fairs during the 10 months of the current year.

CONCLUSION

The tourism sector in Uzbekistan has been developing rapidly in recent years and occupies an important place in the country's economy and social life. As analyzed in this article, the attraction of foreign investments to the tourism sector in Uzbekistan is of great importance for the further development and competitiveness of the industry. In particular, the tourism sector contributes to the sustainable development of the country's economy, the creation of new jobs, the

growth of exports, and the attraction of foreign investments.

The opportunities for increasing the competitiveness of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan and strengthening its position in the international tourism market are being created through the attraction of foreign investments.

Further improving the legal, institutional, and financial mechanisms for attracting foreign investments to the tourism sector, as well as strengthening state policy and international cooperation, is of great importance for the effective development of the industry.

Uzbekistan's tourism sector has sufficient potential for investment, and therefore the attraction of foreign investments is an important direction for the development of this sector.

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